

Chemistry of the Liatrinae

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The known chemistry of subtribe Liatrinae (Asteraceae, tribe, Eupatorieae) is reviewed and compared with the chemistry of other subtribes of this largely western hemisphere assembly of Composites.

As defined by King and Robinson¹ the tribe Eupatorieae of the family Asteraceae comprises 18 subtribes. The chemistry of three of these, Mikaninae², Disynaphinae³ and Eupatoriinae⁴ has been reviewed recently. The present article deals with the chemistry of Liatrinae, a relatively small subtribe of six genera which is unique in the Eupatorieae by being restricted to the U.S.A. with a concentration in the southeastern part of the country.

According to King and Robinson¹, the subtribe includes the six genera *Liatris* (34 species and 9 hybrids), *Carphephorus* (4 species), *Trilisa* (two species resurrected from *Carphephorus*), *Litrisa*, *Garberia* and *Hartwrightia* (1 species each). Table 1 lists *Liatris* species recognized by

Table 1. *Liatris* species according to King and Robinson with notes on recent additions or changes

<i>L. acidota</i> Engelm & A Gray	<i>L. lingustylis</i> (A Nelson) Schumann
<i>angustifolia</i> (Bush) Gaiser	<i>microcephala</i> (Small) Schumann
<i>aspera</i> Michx	<i>mucronata</i> DC
<i>borealis</i> Nutt ex MacnH	<i>ohlingerae</i> (S F Blake) B Robinson
<i>bracteata</i> Gaiser	<i>pauciflora</i> Pursh
<i>chapmanii</i> Torrey & A Gray	<i>pilosa</i> (Aiton) Willd
<i>cokeri</i> Pyne & Stucky ^d	<i>provincialis</i> Godfrey
<i>cylindracea</i> Michx	<i>punctata</i> Hook
<i>cymosa</i> (Nessel) Schumann	<i>pycnostachya</i> Michx
<i>densispicata</i> (Bush) Gaiser	<i>regimontis</i> (Small) Schumann ^{b,c}
<i>earlieri</i> (E. Greene) Schumann	<i>scariosa</i> Willd
<i>elegans</i> (Walt) Michx	<i>spicata</i> (L) Willd
<i>garberi</i> A Gray	<i>squarrosa</i> (L) Willd
<i>gracilis</i> Pursh	<i>squarrolosa</i> Mich
<i>graminifolia</i> (Walt) Willd	<i>tenuifolia</i> Nutt
<i>helleri</i> (Porter) Porter	<i>tenuis</i> Shinn
<i>laevigata</i> Nutt	<i>turgida</i> Gaiser
<i>lancifolia</i> (E. Greene) Kittell	<i>virgata</i> Nutt ^e

^aA sandhills taxon distinct from *L. regimontis* (Small) Schumann according to Stucky and Pyne⁵

^bStucky and Pyne⁵ consider the type of *L. regimontis* (Small) Schumann identical with *L. graminifolia* var *smallii* (Britton) Fern & Grissom

^cThe binomial *L. virgata* Nuttall is stated to have priority over *L. regimontis* ≡ *L. graminifolia* var *smallii*⁶

these authors with more recent changes proposed by others which raise the number of recognized species to 35. As already noted by Gaiser⁷ the genus which is characterized by its striking inflorescences, hence the common name 'blazing star' for some of its representatives, is unusually difficult due to variability in and intergradation between species which may account for some of the misattributions in the chemical literature noted in the Tables. Table 2 lists the remaining five genera comprising nine species.

Table 2. Other Liatrinae according to King and Robinson¹

<i>Carphephorus bellidifolius</i> Torrey & A Gray
<i>corymbosus</i> (Nutt) Torrey & A Gray
<i>pseudoliatris</i> Cass
<i>tomentosus</i> (Michx) Torrey & A Gray
<i>Garberia heterophylla</i> (Bartram) Merr & F Harper
<i>Hartwrightia floridana</i> A Gray
<i>Litrisa carnososa</i> Small
<i>Trilisa odoratissima</i> (Willd) Cass
<i>paniculata</i> (Willd) Cass

Early chemical studies of the subtribe were limited to *Carphephorus odoratissimus* Willd. or deertongue, now *Trilisa odoratissima* (Willd) Cass., whose oleoresin because of its high content of coumarin was used as a fixative in perfumery and whose dried leaves were used as a flavor additive to tobacco, a use which is no longer sanctioned. Aside from coumarin and dihydrocoumarin the non-volatile constituents consist of a variety of common triterpenes and their esters, the lignans eudesmin and epiudesmin and plant sterols⁸⁻¹⁰

Characteristic chemical constituents of the Liatrinae which have been investigated more recently are sesquiterpene lactones of various type although there are some notable exceptions (*vide infra*) Eudesmanolides from Liatrinae and their sources are listed in Table 3 and Chart 1, germacranolides and their sources in Table 4 and Chart 2, heliangolides, the most common lactone type, and their

Table 3. Eudesmanolides from *Liatrinaceae*

<i>L. cylindracea</i> ^a	6
<i>gracilis</i> ^b	5
<i>gracilis</i> variant ^{*c}	5
<i>laevigata</i> ^d	1, 2, 3, 4a, b

*New species.

^aRef. 11. ^bRef. 13. ^cRef. 13. ^dRef. 14.

Table 4. Germacranolides and secogermacranolides from *Liatrinaceae*

<i>L. aspera</i> ^a	8, 11
<i>chapmanii</i> ^b	10a, b
<i>cylindracea</i> ^c	7a, b
<i>gracilis</i> ^d	9, 10a-g
<i>pycnostachya</i> ^e	12
<i>spicata</i> ^f	7b
<i>tenuifolia</i> ^g	10a

^aRef. 14. ^bRefs. 12, 13. ^cRef. 11. ^dRefs. 12, 13. ^eRefs. 16, 17. ^fRef. 18. ^gRefs. 13, 17.

Chart 1. Eudesmanolides from *Liatrinaceae*.

Chart 2. Germacranolides and secogermacranolide from *Liatrinaceae*.

sources in Table 5 and Chart 3, guaianolides and their sources in Table 6 and Chart 4, with the various types of ester side-chains found in the lactones listed in Chart 5. The only elemadienolides so far found in the tribe are lactones **34a** from *L. cylindracea*^{11,32} and lactones **34a** and **34b** from a collection described as *L. platylepis* K. Schum, presumably

L. platylepis (Schumann) Small, which also contained the heliangolides **13a-c** and **14a,b**¹¹. This last taxon is not included in the list of King and Robinson¹ (Table 1), although mentioned in their index as a hybrid of uncertain parentage, nor was it earlier recognized by Gaiser⁷ who was dubious about the affinity of material described as *Lacinaria* (an earlier synonym for *Liatris*) *platylepis* Small.

Table 5. Heliangolides from *Liatrinaceae*

<i>Hartwrightia floridana</i> ^a	5a, c
<i>Liatris acidota</i> ^b	15b, 17, 19, 20a, d, 22
<i>chapmanii</i> ^c	27
<i>cylindracea</i> ^d	13b, 14a, b
<i>elegans</i> ^e	18
<i>gracilis</i> variant ^{*f}	24a-c, 25a, b, 26
<i>mucronata</i> ^g	16b, d, 18a-c
<i>ohlingerae</i> ^h	16b, d, 18a, c-f
<i>pauciflora</i> ^{†i}	18a, c
<i>provincialis</i> ^{†j}	13b
<i>punctata</i>	21 ^k , 23 ^l
<i>spicata</i>	13a, b ^m , 14a, b ^l
<i>squarrulosa</i> ^{†n}	16

*New species. [†]As *L. secunda* Ell. [‡]As *L. scabra* (Greene) Schum.

^aRef. 19. ^bRef. 15. ^cRefs. 20, 21. ^dRef. 11. ^eRef. 22. ^fRef. 23. ^gRef. 15. ^hRef. 24. ⁱRef. 22. ^jRef. 25. ^kRefs. 26, 27. ^lRef. 22. ^mRef. 18. ⁿRef. 17. ^oRef. 11.

Mention must also be made of a variant of typical *L. gracilis* discovered by the late R. K. Godfrey. The chemistry differed significantly²³ from that of *L. gracilis* itself (see Tables 3 and 4), the only common constituent being the eudesmanolide **5**. The material is to be described as a new species (private communication from Professor L. C. Anderson).

In a number of instances (Table 7) diterpenes which are listed in Chart 6 accompany the sesquiterpene lactones. Unusual constituents are the long-chain diterpenoids **35a, b** from *L. elegans*³³ and the *seco*-labdane **36** from *Garberia heterophylla*²⁸ while ordinary labdanes commonly found

Chart 3. Heliangolides from Liatrinae.

Table 6. Guaianolides from Liatrinae

<i>Gerberia heterophylla</i> ^a	28b
<i>L. graminifolia</i> ^b	29a, 32a, 33
<i>pycnostachya</i> ^c	29c, 32b, 31b
<i>spicata</i> ^d	28a, 32b
<i>squarrosa</i> ^e	29b, 30a, 31a
<i>tenuifolia</i> ^f	29c

^aRef. 28. ^bRef. 29. ^cRefs. 16, 17, 29, 30. ^dRefs. 18, 29, 30. ^eRef. 31. ^fRef. 17.

in many representatives of other subtribes of Eupatorieae, are so far confined to *Hartwrightia floridana*¹⁹. Clerodanes of types 39 and 40 from *Hartwrightia floridana*¹⁹ and *L. scariosa*³⁴ are scattered throughout Eupatorieae while clerodanes 41a,b from *L. spicata*¹⁸ are normally characteristic of Bacchariinae of Astereae. The absence of kauranes which are widely distributed in other subtribes of Eupatorieae seems noteworthy, and while pimaranes have been encountered in other subtribes, triols 42-44 from *L. laevigata*¹⁴ are so far unique. The secondary constituents of a collection of *L. microcephala* were limited to the

Chart 4. Guaianolides from Liatrinae.

Chart 5. Ester side-chains in terpenoids.

sesquiterpenes listed in Chart 7³⁵; the only other unusual sesquiterpenoid mentioned in the literature is 9-(2-methylbutyryloxy)geraniol acetate from *L. cylindracea*¹¹.

Table 7. Diterpenes from *Liatrinae*

<i>Garberia heterophylla</i> ^a	36
<i>Hartwrightia floridana</i> ^b	37, 38, 39, 40a
<i>Liatris elegans</i> ^c	35a, b
<i>laevigata</i> ^d	42-44
<i>scariosa</i> ^e	40b
<i>spicata</i> ^f	41a, b

^aRef. 28. ^bRef. 19. ^cRef. 33. ^dRef. 14. ^eRef. 34. ^fRef. 18.

Flavonoids are commonly used as markers in biochemical systematics but references to their occurrence in *Liatrinae* are relatively sparse. Salvigenin, eupatorin and 5-hydroxy-6,7,8-trimethoxyflavone were isolated from *L. aspera*¹⁵, the last also from *L. chapmanii*¹², *L. gracilis* furnished hispidulin and 5,7,4'-trihydroxy-3'-methoxyflavone¹⁵ and *L. pauciflora* contained myrecetin, quercetin³⁶ and mearnsetin³⁷, while flavone glycosides, mainly kaempfericitrin, vicenin and isoquercitrin, have been reported from ten *Liatris* species.

Benzofurans of the euparin type are distributed throughout Eupatorieae and *Liatrinae* are no exception. Table 8 lists euparin derivatives and their sources; it also includes an unusual furylacetylene reported thirty years ago from the

Chart 6. Diterpenes from *Liatrinae*.

Chart 7. Sesquiterpenes from *Liatris microcephala*.

Table 8. Benzofurans from *Liatrinae*

R ¹	R ²	
	H	<i>L. aspera</i> ¹⁵
	OH	<i>H. floridana</i> ¹⁹ <i>L. gracilis</i> ¹² <i>L. microcephala</i> ³⁵ <i>L. spicata</i> ³⁸ <i>L. squarrosa</i> ⁴¹ <i>L. tenuifolia</i> ¹⁷
	<i>H. floridana</i> ¹⁹ <i>L. scariosa</i> ³⁴	<i>L. scariosa</i> ³⁴
	<i>L. squarrosa</i> ³¹	<i>L. squarrosa</i> ³¹
	O CH(CH ₃) ₂	<i>L. provincialis</i> ⁴⁰
		<i>L. pycnostachya</i> ⁴¹ <i>L. scariosa</i> ⁴² <i>L. spicata</i> ⁴²

roots of three *Liatris* species⁴². Finally, mention must be made of the isolation of the pyrrolizidine alkaloids senecionine, otosenine, intermedine, lycopsamine, integerrimine, amabiline, punctanecine and a punctanecine isomer from the roots of *Liatris punctata*⁴³. Pyrrolizidine alkaloids occurs in a number of *Eupatorium* species⁴ and have also been reported within the last decade from *Chromolaena odorata*⁴⁴ of subtribe Praxelinae and *Critonia portoricensis* (as *Eupatorium portoricensis*)⁴⁵ of subtribe Critoniinae within Eupatorieae.

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